
The Influence of Moonlighting on the Performance of Medical Practitioners of Lagos University Teaching Hospital (LUTH)

Dauda Adako

Department of Public Administration,
Faculty of Management Sciences,
Taraba State University, Jalingo Nigeria.
Email: dadako641@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Moonlighting is a delicate and complicated management contemporary issue that is posing challenges to both employers and employees in the work environment. Hence, this study investigated the influence of moonlighting practice on the performance of the medical practitioners of Lagos University Teaching Hospital (LUTH). Primary source of data collection was utilize, specifically survey design was used, with stratified non probability sampling technique and purposive sampling techniques adopted in selecting 342 respondents. The result of the investigation revealed that moonlighting activities among the employees are carried out both within and outside the hospital, though not with the intention of changing their jobs or career lines but to increase skills and income. It was also found that moonlighting by employees of the hospital have an overwhelming negative impact on the hospital performance. It was equally revealed that the hospital management has no clearly spelled out regulations guiding or curbing the activity. Hence, the study concluded that moonlighting have both negative and positive effects on the performance of the hospital, it is therefore recommended that the management should deploy administrative regulatory strategies in controlling employees' moonlighting practice and apply sanctions for those who would go against such rules and regulations. That way, both the employees and the hospital would benefits from the diverse skills and incomes or financial gain that comes with the practice of moonlighting.

Keywords: Employee, Medical Practitioners, Moonlighting, Organization, Performance, Practice, Primary Job, Strategy

INTRODUCTION

Attainment of a high level performance through productivity and efficiency has always been an organization's goal of high priority (Ndulue & Ekechukwu 2016). In order to achieve this goal an organization needs highly satisfied and motivated workforce, who are dedicated to their jobs, because when employees feel dissatisfied with the nature of the job they do, there is likelihood their level of commitment could drastically reduce, and since employees are the engine room of the organization, their dissatisfaction with the nature of job they do could pose a threat to the overall performance of the organization (Ndulue & Ekechukwu 2016). Dissatisfied employees tends to have low morale towards their jobs (Ezeanyim, Ekene, Ufoaroh, & Ajakpo, 2019). When employees morale to the job

are low, their performance is equally affected, because they will not be motivated to perform well and may seek for alternative job satisfaction and motivation outside their primary job by engaging in moonlighting as an alternate way of achieving personal fulfillment. Moonlighting poses challenges for both employees as well as human resource professionals, as it has both positive and negative impacts on an organization. With both private and public sector's employees involved in moonlighting, and Nigeria like other parts of the world is experiencing a rising case of the phenomenal. Researchers in organizations and human resource field are challenge by the rising practice to tilt their searchlight to the new trend, because of it rising cases among the organization's human resources.

Human resources are considered as the life blood and the most important asset for any organization (Kaur & Saini, 2020). That is why organizations' human resource department is seen to be playing strategic roles in managing people and the workplace environment. This is because imperial human resource policy can accomplish both organizational and employees' goals together. Hence, human resource managers are coming up with new trends, practices and techniques on daily basis to meet with the new challenges of human capital that will bring about optimum employees performance that will translate to organizational goals attainment. Ezeanyim et al. (2019) opined that, employee performance is the main factor in ensuring that the organization is run smoothly and successfully. Eze (2012) believe that, good employee performance will improve the organizational performance. Meanwhile Ezeanyim et al. (2019), list some of the variables that influence employees' performance to include perception, values, and attitude. Though, they believe that the variables are inexhaustible thereby focusing on the definition of performance, which they opined is a function of an individual's ability, skill, and effort in a given situation. Employee's skills and abilities in a short run are relatively stable (Ndulue & Ekechukwu 2016). Effort to Ndulue & Ekechukwu (2016), is an internal force of an individual employee that makes him or her to work willingly when satisfied with job and his or her needs are met, the employee naturally develop an attachment to work by making effort to perform better, leading to individual and organizational optimum performance.

Moonlighting or multiple job holding as a practice where employee takes up two or more jobs simultaneously to either supplement income from the primary job or gain job satisfaction by improving skills and expertise, is a trend that is evidently on an increase and is gradually becoming a recurrent phenomenal in the field of human resource management, particularly among employees of public organizations, often leading to industrial dispute between employees and the employers or management, that sometimes result to judicial interventions. These

days, the percentage of employees engaged in extra or secondary jobs holding are increasing, with the health practitioners such as medical doctors, nurses, pharmacists and radiologists who are rendering human essential services are gradually joining the trend by diverting their energy from the initial concentration on their primary jobs, to sharing it with a secondary jobs commonly referred to as moonlighting or multiple job holding. Making it a common place for the populaces to blame government for the public sector's inability to deliver efficient quality healthcare, and the government inability to regulate the health sector, leading to unproductive, poorly motivated, inefficient, client unfriendly and corrupt practices civil service that is highly saturated with unsatisfied public servants, having high tendency of undertaking another job aside their primary job. Thereby being inconsistent in their primary place of work, and sometimes referring clients to their private health facility for personal gain. Dedicating part of their working hours and energy to activities that are not strictly speaking what they are paid by their primary employer to do. Taking up such other jobs as consultancy jobs for private or non-governmental health organizations, engaging in personal private health practices or non-medical activities that generates additional income but add little or nothing to their job experience and skills. However, very little is known about the extent of the consequences of such practices (moonlighting) on the utilization of the scarce resources within the disposal of the primary job organization that are dedicated to the development of the citizens' health, or the quality of impact of an individual performance level of the employees engaged in moonlighting, the legislation guiding the practice, as well as employer/management perception towards it.

Statement of the Problem

Moonlighting has affected the working style and hours of the medical practitioners of Lagos University Teaching Hospital such that the employees find it easy to carry on a secondary job. Though, moonlighting is not a new concept in LUTH, as it is being practice since time immemorial even without the understanding of the employee or the employer of its consequences on the individual and the overall organizational performance. And very few studies if any have been conducted on the reasons LUTH medical staff engage in moonlighting and its subsequent performance consequence on the individual and the organization. There are numerous reasons to why employees are interested in taking up additional jobs. Among the low income earners the reason could be to augment their disposable income, while to those in the higher paying jobs the reasons could be to gain additional job experience, job satisfaction, and widening scope in their field of specialization. However, it is not clear as to which of the above reasons makes medical practitioners of Lagos University Teaching Hospital to moonlight, as they

are seen to be among the high income earners in the health sector and when compare to other jobs in different profession.

Lagos University Teaching Hospital (LUTH) is a hospital in Nigeria with the highest concentration of skilled medical and paramedical staff in different areas of medicine (LUTH, 2020). This explains the reason why LUTH is always the focus, when foreign countries, Oil companies, and even highbrow private hospitals in Nigeria when recruiting, their first place of attraction is LUTH (LUTH, 2020). And because most of these countries, companies, and hospitals are offering higher pay alongside good working conditions, the medical practitioners often opted to leave the services of LUTH for the new offers, at most the few that choose to stay may be engage in moonlighting practices by rendering part-time, consultancy services and other forms of secondary services to the multinational companies, private hospitals, NGOs, etcetera. Although, the decision to moonlight among the medical practitioners of Lagos University Teaching Hospital is an individual thing but, there is need to look at the extent to which the performance of the individual employee and that of the institution is affected by such decision. It is imperative to note that studies on the subject of moonlighting in the field of human resource management particularly in highly paid profession such as medical health practice are insufficient. As most studies associate multiple job holding with low income, thereby believing that only employees on low income jobs moonlight. This limitation for associating dual job holding to just low income professions and individuals, is what this study intend to bridge, by examining the effect and factors that necessitates medical practitioners of LUTH to moonlight and how that affects their individual performance and that of the organization.

Research Question

The study seeks to provide answers to the following questions:

- i. What factors necessitates moonlighting among medical practitioners of Lagos University Teaching Hospital?
- ii. What are the natures of moonlighting engaged by medical practitioners of Lagos University Teaching hospital?
- iii. Does moonlighting have any influence on the performance of medical practitioners of Lagos University Teaching Hospital?
- iv. What strategies are used by Lagos University Teaching Hospital to combat moonlighting among medical practitioners?
- v. What are the aftermath influences of moonlighting on the performance of Lagos University Teaching Hospital?

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of this study is to investigate the effect of moonlighting on the performance of medical practitioners of Lagos University Teaching Hospital. Other specific objectives are:

- i. to examine the factors that necessitates moonlighting practice among medical practitioners of Lagos University Teaching Hospital.
- ii. to identify the nature of moonlighting practice among medical practitioners of Lagos University Teaching Hospital.
- iii. to know the influence of moonlighting on the performance of medical practitioners of Lagos University Teaching Hospital
- iv. to know the strategies used by Lagos University Teaching Hospital to combat moonlighting among the medical practitioners.
- v. to assess the aftermath influence of moonlighting on the performance of Lagos University Teaching Hospital.

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated for the study:

Hypothesis I

H₀: There is no significant influence of moonlighting on the performance of medical practitioners in Lagos University Teaching Hospital.

H_A: There is significant influence of moonlighting on the performance of medical practitioners in Lagos University Teaching Hospital.

Hypothesis II

H₀: There is no any noticeable aftermath influence of moonlighting on the performance of Lagos University Teaching Hospital.

H_A: There is noticeable aftermath influence of moonlighting on the performance of Lagos University Teaching Hospital.

MATERIALS

The Concept of Moonlighting

Mulokozi (2015) in his study of moonlighting effect on the performance of teachers, reported employee's needs, socioeconomic factors, and inadequate pay as the mediating variables for employees moonlighting practices and that moonlighting affects teachers' job performance. Ara and Akbar (2016) in their quest to identify the factors that necessitate moonlighting among University staff, conducted a study that revealed that the desire for additional income, augment blocked promotion, skill diversity and the need for job autonomy are the reasons for moonlighting practices particularly among the academics. Pouliakas (2017) opined that multiple job holding or moonlighting is an important form of a typical employment in most economies. And that new forms of work, driven by

digitization may enable its future growth. However, many misconceptions exist including the belief that multiple job holders are low-skilled workers who moonlight primarily for financial reasons or that the practice increases during economic downturn. And that it allows the development of workers skills and spurs entrepreneurship. While Md Sabron and Hassim (2018), in a study termed "working on an extra job" revealed that increase household income is the major factor that influences employees engagement in moonlighting. And to Adebisi (2019), moonlighting is no longer just a second job for the under paid blue collar jobs, but it equally a career development strategy for some professionals. On the other hand, Nafesa and Uthra (2020), reported that employees in today's growing economy are not much concerned about enriching themselves professionally only, but also economically. In other words, economic enrichment is one of the major factor behind employees moonlighting practice. And to Bidin, Harun, Salleh, and Hamid (2021), moonlighting can take the form of additional wage or salary job. Here also the reason for moonlighting practice among employees is centres on additional income.

Types of Moonlighting

Banerjee (2012) in a study that seems to focus on the types of moonlighting opined that, there are blue moonlighting and quarter moonlighting.

1. Blue moonlighting: is when an employee takes up additional jobs due to dissatisfaction regarding wage payment while,
2. Quarter moonlighting: is to take additional jobs due to increase in personal and family demands. Whichever way the reason for the both types trickle down to the need for additional income. However, to Tewari (2018), who approached the study from an employee intention angle, reported the two types of moonlighting to be persistent and transitory moonlighting.
3. Persistent moonlighting: in his study is when an employee holds dual jobs without any intention to change career stream.
4. Transitory moonlighting: it is when moonlighting is embarked by an employee with the intention of shifting his or her career. Here the focus is on whether the employee's reasons of moonlighting are to change the primary job or not.

Method of Moonlighting Practice

Hardeep and Saini (2020) in their study reported that moonlighting are secretly and typically carried out at night by employees without telling their primary employers. Bidin (2021) reported another method of moonlighting practice among employees is by becoming an employee to more than one employer or becoming self-employed while having a primary job that is continues not on an irregular interval basis. Pouliakas (2017) in his study also outlined employees'

entrepreneurship practices as a method of moonlighting practice among organizational workers. Here, employees who are engaged in entrepreneurial practices either at the workplace or outside the organization either during or after working hours can be considered as moonlighters.

Moonlighting Influence on Employees Performance

In addressing the issue of moonlighting influence on the employee's performance Md Sabron and Hassim (2016), reported that studies suggested moonlighting contributes to poor employees and organizational performance, bringing about job stress, absenteeism, and subsequent termination of employee's primary job appointment or both. In a study conducted by Osagie and Akinlosotu (2017), on the causal relationship between teachers' job performance and students' academic achievement in secondary schools in Nigeria; it was revealed that a bi-causal relationship existed between teachers' job performance and students' academic achievement. Indicating that teachers' performance on their various instructional duties affect students' learning outcome, while on the reverse, how well or badly student performed, also goes to influence the teachers' job performance. While in the view of Adebisi (2019), in a bid to weigh the economic theory of free market economy on health sector operation opined that, if moonlighting is allowed, physicians can be expected to provide faster and higher quality service delivery in the private sectors, meanwhile customers who are willing to pay for these superior services will opt out of public system. However, to the negative influence of moonlighting, he asserted that it may cut back qualities service delivery to patients in the public sector and the medical doctors who chooses not to moonlight may equally cut back on quality service delivery, owing to lack of incentives in the public health system.

Strategies in Combating Moonlighting

On the strategy of how to combat moonlighting among employees Mulokozi (2015), reported that to curb teachers' moonlighting, the management of Dar es salaam region secondary schools deployed the use of folio inspection, provision of incentives, warning letter, special form, and physical follow up in tackling moonlighting practice among the teachers. Nunoo, et al. (2016), opined that making employees with single job more employment secured, will likely reduce their tendency of moonlighting while, increasing the level of job security for employees who are already engaged in moonlighting practice will only increase their propensity to moonlight the more. Nafeesa and Uthra (2020) on the other hand recommended that employers should devise a reasonable and satisfactory pay package as well as conducive working environment that will motivate the employees to concentrate more on their primary job.

Aftermath Effect of Moonlighting

In a study of the aftermath effects of moonlighting Walsh et al. (2015), revealed that one of the aftermath effects of employees moonlighting is that some employers may constantly prefer to be hire workers who already have job. This could be because the employers want to cut down cost associated with full time employment or perhaps they may want to tap from the employee's accumulated wealth of experience with the other employers. In which case, the chances of the unemployed to get employ will be slime down. Other negative aftermath effects could include poor performance, job stress, absenteeism and even termination of appointment (Md sabran & Hassim, 2016). To Vermeeren (2017), moonlighting help employees to live comfortable lives in this era of joblessness. Meanwhile to Md Sabron, Hassim, and Ahmad (2017), the aftermath effect of moonlighting is both positive and negative, as it lead to reduction in employees' access to job training opportunities, with moonlighters being less likely to have planning and supervisory responsibilities while on the other hand, it increase their income and improve their skills and expertise that could be beneficial to the organization. Bidin et al. (2021) express optimism that embracing more jobs and doing multiple tasks at one time no doubt possess some challenges to an employee, as well as to the employer. This danger could be in terms of the employee's health or social life while to the organization it could lead to poor performance or leakage of organization vital information to other rival companies.

Legislation on Moonlighting

Legislation on multiple jobs holding according to Bidin et al. (2021), is among the important provisions in the employment legislations. Some of the legislations as revealed in their study have a clear cut provision for employees moonlighting, where it is permitted in certain jurisdictions while in others, moonlighting is not permitted. In the United States of America the study reported that there is a comprehensive law on double employment, where employees are not prohibited from engaging in moonlighting practices. However, there are restrictions on employees' secondary jobs which conflict with their primary job, probably on the working hours. Order than that, employees are permitted to take up additional jobs as much as they can do justice to their employer's job demands. While in India, Bidin et al. (2021), recorded that moonlighting is clearly prohibited in the India employment law. Section 60 of the country's Factory Act 1948 prohibited employees moonlighting as it states " No adult worker shall be required or allowed to work in any factory on any day on which he has already been working in any other factory save in such circumstances as may be prescribed". The reasons for this Prohibition are that moonlighters takes the limited employment opportunities of

the tamed unemployed individuals chances of getting employ, as well as create a personal conflict for the individual moonlighter. One can easily deduced the reason for this barn, as India being the world second most populated country, with a high number of unemployment. Public policy therefore, to create an even employment opportunities could be one of the reasons for the barn of moonlighting practices among employees in the country. Lyle (2015) observed that there appeared to be balance employees personal needs against the requirements of the daily tasks of their primary job, in that some organizations prohibit moonlighting while others encourage the practice as a way to supplement employees' low pay. Study by Bidin et al. (2015), backed up the later assertion of Lyle as he reported that the Malaysian government encouraged its citizens to moonlight in order to earn more to be able to cope with the rising cost of living.

Empirical Review of the Literature

Khatri and Khushboo (2014) in their study referred to moonlighting as holding more than one job at hand. The scholars opined that employees moonlight for certain reasons which includes gaining experience in new field, pursue some hobbies leading to job satisfaction that may be absent in the primary job, improving job security and, or for monetary purposes. The study further shows that male employees tend to moonlight more than their female counterpart. And that the nature of the primary job, play major role in determining employees' propensity to moonlight. The finding of the study revealed that moonlighting helps employees in gaining skills. Md sabron, Hassim, and Ahmad (2017) in their study agreed with the earlier study that moonlighting do not only supplement main income but equally provide job satisfaction in terms of improving employees' skills and expertise. However, the study reported a contrast evidence of more prevalence of moonlighting practice among female employees as against their male counterpart. The finding of the study revealed that moonlighting affect the performance of employees in an organization. In a separate study Md sabron and Hassim (2018), in their study defined moonlighting as people holding one or two jobs at the same time, while they still have a primary job. The study considered moonlighting as a high value competitive advantage in the business world that organizations ought to allow their employees to engage in it, so as to capture it competitive advantage. The study further suggested that environmental, personal, and behavioral factors are the major influencing factors for employees engagement in the practice of moonlighting. Nafeesa and Uthra (2020) in their study defined moonlighting as the act of taking up a secondary job in addition to the primary job. The study revealed that the major reasons for employees' engagement in moonlighting includes inadequate remuneration from the primary job, and the other intention could be to look for other viable opportunities in the same or

alternate career. Citing sex and age as the major demo-graphical factors that influences moonlighting practice among employees, they later recommended that employers should devise a reasonable and satisfactory pay package as well as conducive working environment that will motivate employees to concentrate more on the primary job. In the study conducted by Hardeep and Saini (2020), moonlighting is said to relate to employee embarking on an additional job, secretly and typically at night without telling his or her current employer. The study reported that though moonlighting makes a noticeable difference in employee's income and ultimately to their standard of living but, it is both challenging to the employees as well as the human resource professionals. While Bidin, Harun, Salleh, and Hamid (2021), use the term double employment in their study in referring to moonlighting as being a situation where an employee holds two or more paid jobs namely primary job and a secondary or additional job simultaneously. In this case an individual might become an employee to more than one employer or he/she might have one employer and become a self-employ for another job. To them, an employee can be involved in multiple job holding "moonlighting" by undertaking to hold another job while having a job at the same time repeatedly and continuously not on irregular intervals basis.

Employees Performance

Afshan, Sobia, Kamran, and Nasir (2012) defined performance as the achievement of specific tasks that are measured against predetermined or identified standards of accuracy, completeness, cost and speed. In a similar definition Nmadu (2013), in his study defined employee performance as a degree of accomplishment of tasks that make up an employee's job. He further stated that performances are measured in terms of productivity, job satisfaction, turnover, and absenteeism. To Herbert, John, and Lee (2000), employees performance is the outcome or contribution of the employees to make them attain organizational goals. Meanwhile Gibson (2012), in his study refer to employees' performance as a measure of the morale of employees' effective and efficient completion of mutually agreed tasks by the employee, as set out by the employer. Zameer, Ali, Nisar, and Amir (2014) in their study reported that employees' performance as a dependent variable include three major dimensions, that is, job productivity, job quality, and job accomplishment. Researchers agreed that when conceptualizing employees' performance one have to differentiate between actions, that is, behavioral aspect and an outcomes aspect of employees' performance (2009). By behavioral aspect the study refers to what an individual do in the work situation. The measurement of these actions by the employee are then scaled and considered as the constituents of his performance. Ndulue and Ekechukwu (2016) in their study believed that the outcome aspects of performance depend on factors order than the individual's

behavior. These other factors in most cases are outside the employee's immediate control and are often contingent in nature.

Theoretical Framework

Relative Deprivation Theory

This study utilize the theory in order to ascertain whether economic or social deprivation of staff or both are the reasons for moonlighting practice among the medical practitioners of Lagos University Teaching Hospital. The theory therefore, will aid this study in assessing whether the medical practitioner of Lagos University Teaching Hospital who Moonlight are economically and socially deprived when compared with their counterparts within the same institution who do not engage in moonlighting.

Occupational Specific Phenomenon Theory

This study therefore, shall utilize the theory in order to ascertain whether the reason for moonlighting among the medical practitioners of Lagos University Teaching Hospital is associated to the nature of their profession or it's an individual medical practitioner's intention.

Gender Theory of Moonlighting

This study shall therefore, utilize the postulation of the theory as a guide in investigating the prevalence of moonlighting among the different gender of the practitioners in the institution.

Aspiration Theory

This study shall use the postulation of the theory in assessing the motivation behind the medical practitioners of the Lagos University Teaching Hospital choice for embracing moonlighting. In order to reveal whether the choice of the practice by the moonlighting employees in the institution is in furtherance of their aspiration to develop their skills as well as burst their career, or for economic or other reasons.

METHODS

Research Design

This study adopted the survey design in answering the research questions that were earlier outlined.

Rationale for the Choice of the Research Design

The rationale for the choice of survey method of investigation is due to the quantitative nature of this study, which informed the deployment of questionnaires. Because the study takes place at a single point in time, without any requirement for manipulation of the variables, and with the researcher looking at numerous characteristics at once, it is therefore necessary to adopt the design to aid in data collection from the population for intensive study and analysis. In addition, this study used a self-design and structured questionnaire in collecting data on the variables of interest, comprised of factual information, attitudes, preferences, and experiences of the respondents, being medical practitioners of the Lagos university teaching hospital. The data collected from the respondents include demographic information of the respondents, their moonlighting status, and the factors that necessitates its practice among the respondents, the forms of the practice among the respondents, the influence of the practice on the respondents' performance in the institution. On the other hand, interview was used in gathering information regarding the strategy deployed by the hospital management in combating the moonlighting practice among the medical practitioners, and the aftermath effect of the practice on the performance of the organization. By this design, it was expected that the objectives of the study will be fully accomplished. Besides, the study is quantitative in nature, in that questionnaires and interview are employed in gathering the data and its analysis procedures involves Statistics.

The Study Area

The study focused on examining moonlighting effect on the performance of medical practitioners of Lagos University Teaching Hospital. With the study area being the Lagos University Teaching Hospital located in Idi-Araba, Surulere, Lagos with three of its other branches comprising of Dermatology Clinic located in Yaba, LUTH Primary Health Care (PHC) Pakoto, Ogun state, and LUTH Psychiatry clinic, located in Yaba. The hospital was established in 1961 and open for operation in 1962 having the needed medical practitioners for this study. The medical practitioners for the study includes: medical doctors, nurses, pharmacists, and radiologists that represents the study sample population. The hospital share similar characteristics with other hospitals in the public sector of the Nigeria health system, as well as possessing similar operating characteristics with other private health system in the country.

The Study Population

The population of this study is the entire workforce of the Lagos University Teaching Hospital comprising of all the 2367 staff of the institution (Lagos University Teaching Hospital Payroll and Staff Record, 2021).

The Target Population

The target population of this study is the medical practitioners of the Lagos University Teaching Hospital, comprising of Medical doctors, Nurses, Pharmacists, and Radiologists spread in the eight different departments and three units of the hospital. With the main departments being:

Allied services, Dentistry, Laboratory Services, Internal medicine, Obstetrics and Gynecology, Oncology, Pediatrics and Surgery, other facilities/ units are: Intensive care unit (ICU), Neonatal unit, and NSIA-LUTH Cancer treatment centre

Sampling Frame

The sampling frame for this study represents all the medical practitioners working in the Lagos University Teaching Hospital.

Table 1: Sampling Frame (Population Size)

S/No	Category of Staff	Staff Size
1	Medical Doctors	312
2	Nurses	930
3	Pharmacists	70
4	Radiologists	55
5	Others	1000
	Total	2367

Source: Lagos University Teaching Hospital, Staff Record, 2021

Sample Size Determination

The sample size of this study is calculated using the Yamane (1967) statistical formula which is based on dividing the total population by the individual variables.

Represented by $n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$

Where, n = Sample size

N = Population of the study

e = Precision estimate

The precision estimate represents the confidence level, which is 0.05

Thus,

$$n = \frac{2367}{1 + 2367(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{2367}{1 + 2367(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{2367}{1 + 5.9175}$$

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$$n = \frac{2367}{6.9175}$$
$$n = 342.1756 \approx 342$$

The result above implies that the sample size for this research work is 342 respondents.

Table 2: Proportional Distribution of Employee Based on Sample Size

S/No	Category of Practitioners	Staff Size	Proportional Determination of Sample Size	Sample Size
1	Medical Doctors	312	$\frac{312}{2367} \times 342 = 45.1$	45.1
2	Nurses	930	$\frac{930}{2367} \times 342 = 134.4$	134.4
3	Pharmacists	70	$\frac{70}{2367} \times 342 = 10.1$	10.1
4	Radiologists	55	$\frac{55}{2367} \times 342 = 7.9$	7.9
5	Others	1000	$\frac{1000}{2367} \times 342 = 144.5$	144.5
	Total	2367		342

Source: Researcher, 2021

Sampling Techniques

To achieve the Objectives of this study, both stratified non-probability sampling technique and purposive sampling techniques were adopted in selecting the respondents. Stratified method was deployed in selecting 342 medical practitioners as the sample size. The target population was divided into strata which represented each department and unit in the study area, with each member of the strata given adequate and equal opportunity of being included in the population. The stratified method was used in selecting the respondents from the various departments and units in the hospital, while, purposive sampling technique was utilized in selecting 5 members of the management staff from the cluster of the professionals identified and the chief medical director. This is to enable diversity and provide an even ground for the key practitioners to be involve in the study. So as to enable a logical generalization to be made regarding the area under study

Research Instruments

The structured questionnaire used in this study was aimed at restricting the responses provided by the respondents to be focus on the objective of the study and to increase the respondents understanding of the questions. The questionnaire was divided into two sections. Section (A) was design to gather basic demographic information regarding the respondents such as gender, age, academic

qualifications, cadre and working experience. Section (B) sought to determine the respondents' opinion on the subject matter. The questions were categorized in a non-mutually exclusive manner and rated to achieve the objectives of the study. Section A consists of closed-ended questions while the section B is a combination of open and closed-ended questions. The section is also designed on a four points likert scale battery of strongly agree (4), Agreed (3), Disagree (2), and strongly disagree (1). The respondents in this question tag segments are to indicate the extent to which they agree or disagree with a statement by choosing the level of their conviction as outlined above.

Validity of the Research Instruments

This study adopted content validity with the research instrument further evaluated by the researcher to ensure adequate validity of the Instrument.

Reliability of the Research Instruments

In order to establish the reliability of the instrument used in this study, a pilot study was carried out using two different hospitals for a test, and retest validation using 20 respondents, 10 respondents on each phase of the test. The pretest respondents comprise of two medical doctors, two Nurses, two pharmacists, two radiologists, and two management staff on each phase of the test. The results of the Reliability test were tested to proof the Reliability of the instruments.

Table 3: First Pretest Sample of Respondents

S/No	Category of Staff	Numbers of Staff
1	Medical Doctors	2
2	Nurses	2
3	Pharmacists	2
4	Radiologists	2
5	Management Staff	2
	Total	10

Source: Researcher, 2021

Table 4: Second Pretest Sample of the Respondents

S/No	Category of Staff	Numbers of Staff
1	Medical Doctors	2
2	Nurses	2
3	Pharmacists	2
4	Radiologists	2
5	Management Staff	2
	Total	10

Source: Researcher, 2021

Cronbach Alpha using the split-half technique with the aid of SPSS, the result is shown below:

Table 5: Case Processing Summary

	N	%
Valid Case	20	100.0
Case Excluded	0	.0
Total	20	100.0

a. Leastwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Table 6: Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.687	20

Ethical Consideration

In order to avoid personal and irregular questions that could cause physical or psychological harm to the respondents, an expert supervisor vetted the questionnaire by ensuring its free of threatening languages, while misleading sentences were reframe to reflect the objectives of the study. And the consent of the respondents was sought before the distribution of the questionnaires. The purpose of the study was equally told to the respondents to reassure them the more, of the high confidentiality of their supplied responses and identities.

Sources/Method of Data Collection

This study utilized the primary sources of data collection through the use of the instrumentality of questionnaire in collecting the necessary information from the respondents in the study area. The administration of the questionnaire was

personally carried out by the researcher. And a total of 342 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to elicit responses from the medical practitioners of Lagos University Teaching Hospital. Before embarking on the data collection, a preliminary contact with the respondents was made to explain the rationale for the exercise. And a written assurance of confidentiality was attached to the questionnaire to motivate the respondents to give their most sincere responses without reservation. In order to ensure maximum response rate, time was allotted to the collection of the completed questionnaires. The questionnaires were serially coded for easy identification. And personally deliver and collected by researcher after its completion by the respondents.

Fieldwork Experience

The researcher with the help of a staff of the Lagos University Teaching Hospital was able to get the population size of the employees of the hospital and also secured the permission to carry out the study in the institution. Afterwards, the researcher in consideration of the nature of the respondents' work visited the hospital on several occasions in order to ensure adequate and timely filling of the questionnaire by the respondents. The respondents were given the assurance of treating their information with utmost confidentiality. Assurances from the researcher to the respondents of confidentiality of information being sought made the respondents more relaxed and open in their responses. The researcher was able to gain insight from interaction with some employees as regards how they carry out their tasks in their workplace and how that affects their performance. Some of this real life experiences were in line with the ideas put forward by previous researches, journals and other materials on the subject matter.

Problems Encountered in the Study

One of the major problems that were encountered by the researcher is the fact that the researcher had to visit the hospital on several occasions in order to get the questionnaire filled on time by the respondents. Some other problems encountered were recorded on the process of administering the questionnaires, as some of the respondents were reluctant to respond freely. And determining the right timing to get respondents to fill the questionnaire was also a challenge. Another challenge encountered was the work restrictions, occasion by the covid-19 pandemic that greatly affects the level of interpersonal relation between the researcher and the respondents.

Resolutions to the Problems Encountered in the Study

In addressing the problems outlined above, the researcher made adequate allowance to ensure the suitability of time for the respondents to be relaxed after

their busy schedules before actively engaged in filling the questionnaire. The respondents were also enlightened on the essence and benefits of the research work to their work life, their organization, the body of knowledge, and humanity as a whole. For which course, the items on the questionnaire were put in a simple and easy language for the respondents' understanding.

Method of Data Analysis

At the end of the entire data collection process, plausible check was conducted and inconsistent data were appropriately corrected. Both quantitative and qualitative methods were employed in the analysis of the data. At the quantitative analysis, tables, pie chart, and other diagrams depicting frequency of occurrence and statistics such as indices for comparisons to establish statistical relationship between variables were used in interpreting the collected data. The results were analyzed and converted into statistical tables, and percentages. The data generated from the responses of the various respondents to the research questions were analyzed using percentages, to show the distribution of opinions and perceptions of the respondents. While, data generated through interview were analyzed using content analysis, so as to provide knowledge and understanding of the phenomenal under study. These were achieved by means of reducing the data collected to a sizeable number, and displayed same, so as to draw a verifiable conclusion. Meanwhile, the hypotheses formulated for this study were equally statistically tested, and the results interpreted.

Limitation of the Study

This study was carried out in Lagos University Teaching Hospital and therefore, the scope of the study was restricted to the medical practitioners of Lagos University Teaching Hospital. The Covid19 pandemic also delayed the quick execution of the research work, due to interpersonal traffic regulation particularly among front line workers which this research respondents are at the forefront, this therefore, greatly limits the possibility of the researcher to have the full attention of the respondents as when due.

Strength of the Study

The study examined moonlighting effects on the performance of the medical practitioners of Lagos University Teaching Hospital and how it has contributed to improving or negatively affecting the performance of the hospital. It further ascertains the effect of such practice on the individual performance of the employees. Therefore, the findings and recommendations of this study would be beneficial to the hospital and their employees, as well as other government and private agencies with related and similar work processes.

RESULT

Three hundred and forty two (342) copies of the questionnaire were administered to the employees of the Lagos University Teaching Hospital, out of which, three hundred and twenty two (322) been 94.2% of the distributed questionnaire were retrieved and analyzed using Tables, Bar charts, and Pie charts.

Interpretation of the Socio- Demographic Data

Results from the analysis of the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents indicated that majority of the respondents are male, with the total number of 169 respondents, constituting 52.5% of the sample size being male folks against their female folks who are 153 respondents, representing 47.5%. The result suggested that most of the staff of the hospital is male. And in terms of age, the bulk of the respondents fall within the age range of 40-49 years forming 41.9% of the sample size, closely followed by those within the age of 30-39 years at 25.5%, 50-59 years 21.1%, 20-29 years 6.5% while, those within 60 years and above are 5% respectively. There by suggesting that majority of the staff are in their productive age and can be presume to be capable of contributing meaningfully to the achievement of the hospital goals, by reason of their age. Educationally, majority of them are holders of Bachelor's degree standing at 28.9%, OND 20.2%, HND 16.1%, Master's degree 12.7%, other forms of Qualifications 11.5%, and SSCE 10.6% respectively. Meaning, majority of the staff have the necessary skills and the technical know-how, to achieve the hospital set goals. In respect to service year, 35.1% of the staff have been serving in the hospital for an average of 6 to 10 years, 23.3% have been serving for between 11 to 15 years, 16.1% serves for 5 years and below, 14.3% have been serving for a period of about 16 to 20 years while 11.2% serves for 21 years and above respectively. Indicating that most of the hospital staff have the necessary experience for achieving the institution's set goals. In terms of specialization, other category of Staff order than the target population of this study are more in number with 41.3%, closely followed by Nurses with 40.1%, Medical doctors 13.4%, Pharmacist 3.1%, and Radiologists 2.2%. Thereby Project the hospital to be adequately staff with the necessary Personnel capable of achieving set result.

Interpretation of the Factors that Necessitates Moonlighting Practice

A closer look on table 8 above, indicated that moonlighting is a serious problem in Lagos University Teaching Hospital with 55% of the respondents strongly consenting to the premise, 28% fairly agreed, 15.2% indecisive, 12% disagree, while 0.6% strongly Disagree. Suggesting therefore that, employees moonlighting are serious problem to the smooth operation of the hospital. In response to whether the staff of the hospital holds other jobs aside their official engagement with LUTH, 18.9% of the respondents strongly agree, 22.7% responded to the affirmative, 31.1%

were neutral, 12.4% disagree, whereas 14.9% strongly disagree with the assertion. Hence, it is safe to say that, the numbers of Lagos University Teaching Hospital employees who holds additional jobs aside their primary job with the hospital are 149.8° in a scale of 1 to 360° and can therefore be consider as a high number capable of influencing the performance of the hospital. Responses to the question; whether the employees are engage in extra pay activities within the hospital? Revealed that 12.4% of the respondents are in strong terms agreement, 10.9% fairly agreed, 38.8% are indecisive, while 25.5% disagree and 12.4% are in total objection. This therefore goes to mean that, the numbers of the employees who do extra activities for additional pay within the hospital are of an average number. That is, they can neither be say to be too high nor too low of the general population.

The employees' engagement in an unpaid extra activities survey revealed 54.3% of the respondents strongly consented to the affirmative, 28.3% merely agreed, 9.3% remain undecided, 6.2% disagree, and 1.9% strongly disagreed. Suggesting that, a bulk of the employees are doing one or more jobs outside their official assignment in the hospital which they are not been paid for. And as a reason for moonlighting practice among the employees of LUTH, 55.9% of the respondents strongly agreed that moonlighting practice diversify staff skills towards high quality service delivery, 29.8% agreed to the preceding reason for moonlighting practice, 4.7% were undecided, while 3.1% disagreed, and 6.5% strongly disagreed. It then suggested that, skill diversification is the Necessitating factor for employees moonlighting practice, aside their desire for extra pay.

Interpretation of the Respondents' Views on the Nature of Moonlighting Practice

The table 9 above depicted 16.8% of the respondents strongly consented to the fact that Lagos University Teaching Hospital (LUTH) employees are engage in additional job shift within the hospital, 20.2% simply agreed, while 31% were neutral, 11.5% disagreed, and 20.5% strongly disagreed. Suggesting that the numbers of LUTH employees who are engaged in additional shift as a mode of moonlighting practice are approximately about 37% of the total number of the employees. In terms of parallel medical services in other health related institutions, 36.3% of the respondents strongly agreed that the employees are rendering such services for an additional income, while 31.4% of the respondents agreed, 7.5% were indecisive, however, 14.6% disagreed, and 10.2% strongly disagreed. Meaning that, more than half of the employees roughly 67.7% of the total employees are rendering parallel paid medical services to other health institutions. Whereas investigation on LUTH staff ownership of private clinic revealed that 9.9% of the respondents strongly believe that LUTH employees are operating their own personal private clinic aside their primary job, 14.9% of the respondents agreed, 31.6% were undecided, 22% disagreed and 22% strongly disagreed. Depicting that

only about 25% of the hospital employees owns a private hospital. In terms of consultancy services to private individuals, clinics, and NGOs, 39.4% of the respondents strongly agreed that LUTH staffs are into consultation services to private individuals, clinics, and Non-Governmental Organizations, while 29.5% agreed, 6.2% were neutral, however 11.5% disagreed, and 13.4% strongly disagreed. Suggesting that bulk of the hospital medical practitioners often consult for private individuals, clinics, or NGOs for an additional paid aside their primary job with the LUTH.

Interpretation of the Respondents' Views on the Influence of Moonlighting on Employees Job Performance

Table 10 above depicted 31.1% of the respondents strongly agreeing to the premise that moonlighting has effect on an individual medical Practitioner's performance, while 25.5% agreed, 15.5% undecided, and 14.6% disagreed, and 13.4% strongly disagreed. Suggesting that, moonlighting affect individual medical Practitioner's job performance. On moonlighting effect on practitioners' duty coverage ability, 47.8% of the respondents strongly agreed that moonlighting affect individual duty coverage ability of a practitioner, 31.7% agreed, 9.3% were neutral; however 5.3% disagreed, while 5.9% strongly disagreed. Thereby, presenting moonlighting as having an in-depth negative impact on medical Practitioners' duty coverage in their place of Primary assignment. Meanwhile, responses on moonlighting effect on medical Practitioners' dedication to duty revealed that 47.5% responded as strongly agreeing to the premise that moonlighting effect individual's dedication to duty, 32% barely agreed, 6.2% were neutral, 6.5% disagreed, while 7.8% strongly disagreed. Putting moonlighting practice among Medical practitioners as causing a serious distortion to the Practitioners' dedication to duty

Interpretation of the Respondents' Views on Strategies Use by Management in Combating Moonlighting

The table 11 above revealed that none of the Respondent strongly agreed that Lagos University Teaching Hospital is happy with staff moonlighting practice. Though, 1.6% of the Respondents casually agreed, while 9.6% were indifferent, 41.9% disagreed, and 46.9% totally disagreed with the assertion that the management permits moonlighting practice among employees. Suggesting that the hospital management is not in any way happy with employees moonlighting activities. Respondents' views on Management act of checkmating moonlighting activities among employees revealed that 19.6% of the respondents strongly agreed that management is checkmating moonlighting activities, 13.1% partially agreed, while 11.5% were neutral, 24.8% disagreed, and 31.1% strongly disagreed. Suggesting

that management efforts towards checkmating employees moonlighting activities is very minimal

Meanwhile responses to management penalization of staffs engaged in moonlighting revealed that 4.7% of the respondents strongly agreed that LUTH management often punish employees found moonlighting, 6.2% partially agreed, 9.6% were indecisive, 32% disagreed, and 47.5% strongly disagreed. Suggesting that the management of the hospital is weak in terms of disciplining employees found wanting of employees moonlighting, though it frowned at staff moonlighting activities. Responses on whether the management have a clear directive or spelled out procedures for regulating or addressing moonlighting practices among the employees revealed that 4.3% were strongly affirmative that the management proceedings on moonlighting are clearly spelled out, 5.6% however merely agreed, while 23.3% were indecisive, 29.5% disagreed, and 37.3% strongly disagreed. Which shows that the management regulations on staff moonlighting practices are either insufficient or not clearly spelled out. On whether any of the employees of the hospital have ever been warned or reprimanded by the management for engaging in moonlighting practice, it was revealed that 3.7% of the respondents strongly consented to the affirmative, 3.1% casually agreed, and 17.7% were indifferent, 31.4% disagreed, while 44.1% strongly disagreed. Meaning that very few staffs have ever been warned or reprimanded for engaging in moonlighting practice

Interpretation of the Respondents' Views on the Aftermath Effects of Moonlighting on the Performance of LUTH

Table 12 above, displayed 14% of the respondents strongly agreeing that moonlighting have negative impact on the performance of the hospital, while 15.5% barely agreed, whereas 10.9% were indecisive, 31.1% disagreed, and 28.6% strongly disagreed. Revealing that LUTH employees moonlighting activities is reducing the performance of the hospital to about 30%. Meanwhile, responses on whether moonlighting affect the quality of staff performance recorded 30.4% of the respondents strongly agreeing that moonlighting affect quality of an individual staff's performance, while 27.6% agreed, 14.6% were indifferent, whereas 15.2% disagreed, and 12.1% strongly disagreed. Suggesting that staff moonlighting activities greatly affect the quality of the performance of Lagos University Teaching Hospital. Regarding moonlighting effects on LUTH consistency to quality service delivery revealed 28% of the respondents strongly agreeing that staff moonlighting affect the hospital consistency to quality service delivery, with 27% also agreeing to the assertion; however 18.6% were indifferent, while 13.7% disagreed, and 12.7% totally disagreed. Suggesting that moonlighting have a great negative influence to Lagos University Teaching Hospital consistency to quality service delivery

The Influence of Moonlighting on the Performance of Medical Practitioners of Lagos University Teaching Hospital (LUTH)

However, responses on the possibility of Moonlighting practices to exhaust employees revealed that 54.7% of the respondents strongly believe that moonlighting greatly exhaust employees engage in such activity, with 30% equally affirming that, while 1.6% were undecided, whereas 4.7% disagreed, and 9% totally disagreed. Projecting employees moonlighting practice as greatly exhausting to the individual, thereby affect the individual's input to the organization.

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis I

Ho: There is no significant influence of moonlighting on the performance of the Lagos University Teaching Hospital staff.

The F-value and the significant value give the overall level of significance of the data. From the table below, the significant values are less than 0.05 for all the questions on influence i.e. there is significant influence of moonlighting on the performance of the Lagos University Teaching Hospital staff. Hence, null hypothesis (Ho) is rejected and alternative hypothesis (HA) is accepted.

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Influence of moonlighting on the performance of medical practioners 1	Between Groups	383.448	4	95.862	245.444	.000
	Within Groups	123.810	317	.391		
	Total	507.258	321			
Influence of moonlighting on the performance of medical practioners 2	Between Groups	291.796	4	72.949	226.502	.000
	Within Groups	102.095	317	.322		
	Total	393.891	321			
Influence of moonlighting on the performance of medical practioners 3	Between Groups	296.279	4	74.070	236.192	.000
	Within Groups	99.411	317	.314		
	Total	395.689	321			

Hypothesis II

Ho: There is no noticeable aftermath influence of moonlighting on the performance of the Lagos University Teaching Hospital staff

The table below showed F-value (less than 1) and p-value (greater than 0.05) between groups for all the four (4) questions relating to aftermath. This implies

that there is no statistically significant difference between the groups. Hence, the null hypothesis (Ho) is accepted.

ANOVA		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Aftermath effect of moonlighting practice on the performance of LUTH 1	Between Groups	.612	4	.153	.245	.912
	Within Groups	197.875	317	.624		
	Total	198.488	321			
Aftermath effect of moonlighting practice on the performance of LUTH 2	Between Groups	3.150	4	.788	.695	.596
	Within Groups	359.474	317	1.134		
	Total	362.624	321			
Aftermath effect of moonlighting practice on the performance of LUTH 3	Between Groups	2.958	4	.740	.589	.671
	Within Groups	397.889	317	1.255		
	Total	400.848	321			
Aftermath effect of moonlighting practice on the performance of LUTH 4	Between Groups	5.894	4	1.473	1.153	.332
	Within Groups	403.869	316	1.278		
	Total	409.763	320			

Summary of Findings

The data analysis revealed that, most of the staff of Lagos University Teaching Hospital (LUTH) are male and are within the productive age, possessing the necessary educational qualifications, work experience, as well as adequately staff to achieve the goal of the hospital. However, moonlighting is still a serious problem in the hospital, with about one quarter (1/4) of the employees holding additional jobs aside their primary job. Some within the hospital while others out it. Meanwhile, the necessitating factors that informed the practice were revealed to be principally the pursuance for skill diversity as well as increase income. While, the nature of the practice among the staff of the hospital are additional shifts, parallel medical services in other health facilities, operation of private hospital, rendering of health consultancy services to individuals, clinics, and NGOs. All these therefore, affect individual staffs performance of LUTH, with an in-depth negative impact on staff duty coverage; causing a serious distortion to the Practitioner's sense of dedication to duty. Hence, the hospital management is not happy with the practice

among the staff, though its efforts towards checkmating the Practice among the employees are very minimal. As the Management's disciplinary measures are weak and characterizes of insufficient and an unclear rules, with very few individuals if any that have ever been warned or reprimanded for engaging in moonlighting practice. Leading to an aftermath influence of the practice among the staff to have cause about 30% reduction in the performance of the hospital, that adversely affects the quality of the hospital service delivery that brings about inconsistency in the hospital's quality of service delivery. Living the employees exhausted, such that they are mentally, emotionally, and physically demoralize to perform their duties effectively and efficiently.

DISCUSSION

This research investigation is in agreement with the studies conducted by Ara and Akbar (2016) and Ponliakas (2017) that identify skill diversity, additional income and the quest to augment blocked promotion as the major factors that necessitate moonlighting practice among employees. However, the study do not in part agrees with Pouliakas' submission that moonlighting is only common among low income workers. As the employees of LUTH comprising of different categories of medical practitioners cannot all be say to be employees with low income, yet, the rate of moonlighting among them is very high. Meanwhile, the study agrees in totality with the submission of Nafesa and Uthra (2020), postulating employees as not only concern about enriching themselves professionally but as well as economically. In other words, economic enrichment is one of the major factors behind employees moonlighting practice. This study equally revealed that LUTH employees moonlighting takes both blue and quarter forms of moonlighting postulated by Banerjee (2012), suggesting that employees moonlight because of their dissatisfaction with the wage payment, as well as increase in their personal and family demands on the limited take home that may not match the rising cost of goods and service in the market owing to global economic meltdown that was occasion by Covid-19 pandemic. In other hand, when compare with the Tewari (2018) study on the types of moonlighting, this study reflected the persistent type of moonlighting practice that explain employee's moonlighting as holding additional job without the intention of changing career or job stream. Meanwhile, on the method or mode of moonlighting practice, this study disagreed with the assertion of Hardeep and Saini (2020), who reported that moonlighting are carried out at night and without the knowledge of the employers. This study therefore distance from the assertion because, some of the LUTH employees were found to be moonlighting within the hospital by engaging in extra pay activities that the management compensate monetarily. Nevertheless, the study agrees in totality with the postulation of Bidin (2021) that employees sometimes in the

course of moonlighting activities may become an employee to more than one employer. This is found to be true as LUTH employees are were found to be rendering parallel medical services to private individuals, clinic, and NGOs, as well as owning their own private health institution. That is also in conformity with Pouliakas (2017) findings. However, the influence of moonlighting on employees' performance revealed that this study is in conformity with Hassim (2016) report that suggested that moonlighting contributes to poor employees and organizational performance, bringing about job stress, absenteeism and even subsequent termination of job contract. It is equally not out of place to state that Akinsolotu (2017) bi-causal relationship concept between teachers' job performance and student academic achievement can be adopted to match the LUTH employees' performance with the hospital quality service delivery to its clients. Postulating that, the higher the quality of an individual medical practitioner's job performance, the higher the quality of service to its clients, While the lower the employee's service, the lower the hospital quality of service delivery to the clients. And on the management strategies for combating moonlighting, this study revealed a great gap that Lagos University Teaching Hospital needed to fill by deploying the strategies employed by the management of Dar es salam as reported by Mulokozi (2015) in curtailing moonlighting among teachers, by using folio inspection, provision of incentives, issuing warning letters, special forms and physical follow-up etc. in Combating employees moonlighting practices. While on the aftermath effect of moonlighting, the study is in consistence with Md Sabran and Hassim (2016), study that associated moonlighting with poor performance, job stress, absenteeism, and termination of appointment, reduction in employees' access to job training, and promotion. However, on the positive side of moonlighting practice, it improve the skills, work experience, and introduce new techniques and ideas of getting effective and efficient result in a work settings.

SUMMARY

The aim of this study was to examine the effect of moonlighting on the performance of medical practitioners of Lagos University Teaching Hospital. Hence, the researcher discovered that moonlighting is a nightmare to the hospital's management owing not just to the large numbers of the practitioners engaged in the practice but, the propensity of the other staffs to join the train. As the study revealed that, the practice is carried out both within and outside the hospital, though without the practitioner's intentions of changing their job or careers. Meanwhile, the necessitating factors for this practice among the practitioners were majorly the quest to diversify their skills and increase their income alongside other motives. With the nature of the practice among them been additional shift, rendering of parallel medical services in other health facilities, running of personal

private health facilities, rendering of consultancy service to private individual, clinics, and Non-Governmental Organizations, etc. However, the management efforts toward checkmating the Practice among the practitioners is very minimal, as there is no standard rules and regulations which are clearly spelled out by the management to guide employees' activities in respect of moonlighting practice in the hospital. As the Management's disciplinary measures for moonlighting are weak and characterizes by insufficient and an unclear regulations, which very few individuals, if any, have ever been warned or reprimanded for engaging in the practice. Wherefore, the aftermath influence of the practice leads to about 30% reduction in the hospital performance. That was reflected on its quality of service delivery to its clients, and the degree of staff inputs, occasioned by inconsistency and weariness; mentally, emotionally and physically which reduce the employees performance and that of the hospital.

CONCLUSION

The objective of this study has been to assess the effect of moonlighting on the performance of medical practitioners of Lagos University Teaching Hospital. Have revealed based on the tested hypotheses that; there is significant influence of moonlighting on the performance of the Lagos University Teaching Hospital staff. While there is no noticeable aftermath influence of moonlighting on the performance of the Lagos University Teaching Hospital staff. Thus, this study concludes that management should deploy administrative regulatory strategies in controlling employees moonlighting practice instead of imposing embargo on it. This is because of its benefits in diversifying the skills of the employees aside the financial gain that comes with the practice.

Contributions to Knowledge

This study contributed to the body of knowledge in the field of human resources management by

- i. Establishing that moonlighting at hospitals thrive where there is no strong legislation or legal provision stopping it.
- ii. It also establishes that the inability of hospital managements to provide guiding rules for the employees' on moonlighting practice is fueling the practice.
- iii. The study also establishes that regulating the practice of moonlighting would generate additional revenue for government through taxation.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, and the conclusion drawn above, it is therefore recommended that,

- i. The management of the Lagos University Teaching Hospital should establish regulatory rules, and make it known to the employees to serve as a guide for employees moonlighting activities.
- ii. Because moonlighting has both positive and negative impact on the organizational performance, it will therefore be unprofessional for the management of LUTH to impose an embargo on the practice among its employees.
- iii. The management should deploy such administrative regulative strategies as the use of Folio inspection during working hours to ensure the employees are at work as when due, and are doing what is expected of them. And where an employee is found wanting, he or she should be made to face the penalty for miss behaviour.
- iv. The management should devise means of generating additional income locally to augment the employees' monthly take home, as well as provide a conducive working environment that will motivate the employees to concentrate more on their primary job.
- v. In terms of legislation, the Nigerian Labour Law should be amended to provide for moonlighting practice in order to reduce industrial disputes among employers and their employees.

Suggestions for Further Studies

This study was conducted to assess the effect of employees moonlighting on organizations' performance, which do not cover all aspect of moonlighting. It is therefore, suggested that further study be conducted on the impact of moonlighting practice on the level of unemployment, so as to know if imposing embargo on moonlighting could bring about a significant difference in the level of unemployment.

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TABLES

4.1 Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Table 7: Respondents Socio-Demographic Characteristics

S/No	Variables	Frequencies	Percentages
1.	Gender		
	Male	169	52.5%
	Female	153	47.5%
2.	Age		
	20-29 Years	21	6.5%
	30-39 Years	82	25.5%
	40-49 Years	135	41.9%
	50-59 Years	68	21.1%
	60 and above Years	16	5%
3.	Educational Qualification		
	SSCE	34	10.6%
	OND	65	20.2%
	HND	52	16.1%
	Bachelor's Degree	93	28.9%
	Master's Degree	41	12.7%
	Others	37	11.5%
4.	Years of Service with LUTH		
	0-5 Years	52	16.1%
	6-10 Years	113	35.1%
	11-15 Years	75	23.3%
	16-20 Years	46	14.3%
	21 and above Years	36	11.2%
5.	Category of Staff		
	Medical Doctors	43	13.4%
	Nurses	129	40.1%
	Pharmacists	10	3.1%
	Radiologists	7	2.2%
	Others	133	41.3%

Source: Field Survey, 2021

4.2 Analysis of the Respondents' Views on the Factors that Necessitates Moonlighting Practice among Staff of LUTH

Table 8: Moonlighting Practice among LUTH Staffs

Moonlighting Practice	Variable				
	SA	A	N	D	SD
Moonlighting is a problem in LUTH	177(55%)	90(28%)	49(15.2%)	4(12%)	2(0.6%)
LUTH staff holds other side jobs	61(18.9%)	73(22.7%)	100(31.1%)	40(12.4%)	48(14.9)
LUTH staff are engage in extra pay activities within the institution	40(12.4%)	35(10.9%)	125(38.8%)	82(25.5%)	40(12.4%)
LUTH staff are engage in an unpaid extra activities within the hospital	175(54.3%)	91(28.3%)	30(9.3%)	20(6.2%)	6(1.9%)
Moonlighting diversify staff skills towards quality service.	50(55.9%)	96(29.8%)	15(4.7%)	10(3.1%)	21(6.5%)

KEY: SA= Strongly Agree; A= Agree; N= Neutral; D= Disagree; SD= Strongly Disagree

Source: Field Survey, 2021

4.3 Analysis of the Respondents Views on the Nature of Moonlighting Practice among the Medical Practitioners of LUTH

Table 9: Respondents Views on the Nature of Moonlighting Practice

Nature of Moonlighting Practice	Variables				
	SA	A	N	D	SD
Staff additional shifts	54(16.8%)	65(20.2%)	100(31%)	37(11.5%)	66(20.5%)
Parallel medical services in other health institutions	117(36.3%)	101(31.4%)	24(7.5%)	47(14.6)	33(10.2)
Operating of personal private clinic	32(9.9%)	48(14.9%)	100(31.6%)	71(22%)	71(22%)
Consultancy services to private individuals, clinics, and NGOs.	127(39.4%)	95(29.5%)	20(6.2%)	37(11.5%)	43(13.4%)

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Analysis of the Respondents' Views on Influence of Moonlighting on the Performance of the Medical Practitioners of LUTH

Table 10: Respondents' Views on the Influence of Moonlighting on Job Performance

Moonlighting Influence on Job Performance	Variables				
	SA	A	N	D	SD
Moonlighting effect on individual performance	100(31.1%)	82(25.5%)	50(15.5%)	47(14.6%)	43(13.4)
	154(47%)	102(31.7%)	30(9.3%)	17(5.3%)	19(5.9%)

The Influence of Moonlighting on the Performance of Medical Practitioners of Lagos University Teaching Hospital (LUTH)

Moonlighting effect on duty coverage ability	153(47.5%)	103(32%)	20(6.2%)	21(6.5)	25(7.8%)
Moonlighting effect on Practitioners' dedication to duty					

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Analysis of the Respondents' Views on the Strategies Use by the Management of LUTH in Combating Moonlighting

Table 11: Respondents Views on Management Strategies of Combating Moonlighting

Management Strategies of Combating Moonlighting	Variables				
	SA	A	N	D	SD
Management is happy with Staff moonlighting activities	0(0%)	5(1.6%)	31(9.6%)	135(41.9%)	151(46.9%)
Management checkmate moonlighting among staff	63(19.6%)	42(13.1%)	37(11.5%)	80(24.8%)	100(31.1%)
Management penalize staff who moonlight	15(4.7%)	20(6.2%)	31(9.6%)	103(32%)	153(47.5%)
Management have a clear direction for addressing moonlighting practice	14(4.3%)	18(5.6%)	75(23.3%)	95(29.5%)	120(37.3%)
Employees have ever been warned on reprimanded by the management	12(3.7%)	10(3.1%)	57(17.7%)	101(31.4%)	142(44.1%)

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Analysis of the Respondents Views on the Aftermath Influence of Moonlighting on the Performance of LUTH

Table 12: Respondents Views on the Aftermath Effects of Moonlighting on LUTH Performance.

Aftermath Effects Moonlighting	Variables				
	SA	A	N	D	SD
Staff moonlighting has negative impact on performance	45(14%)	50(15.5%)	35(10.9%)	100(31.1%)	92(28.6%)
Moonlighting affect quality of staff performance	98(30.4%)	89(27.6%)	47(14.6%)	49(15.2%)	39(12.1%)
Moonlighting affect consistency to quality service delivery	90(28%)	87(27%)	60(18.6%)	44(13.7%)	41(12.7%)
Moonlighting exhaust employees	176(54.7%)	97(30%)	5(1.6%)	15(4.7%)	29(9%)

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Fig 4.1: Gender Classification of the Respondents

Fig. 4.2: Age Distribution of the Respondents

Fig. 4.3: Educational Qualification of the Respondents

Fig. 4.4: Respondents' Years of Service

Fig. 4.5: Categories of the Respondents

Respondents Views on the Factors Necessitating Moonlighting Practices in LUTH

Fig. 4.6 Responses on Objective One Variable

The Influence of Moonlighting on the Performance of Medical Practitioners of Lagos University Teaching Hospital (LUTH)

Respondents' Views on the Influence of Moonlighting on Employees Performance of LUTH

Fig. 4.8: Responses on Objective Three Variables

Respondents' Views on Management Strategies for Combating Moonlighting

Fig. 4.9: Responses on Objective Four Variables

Respondent's Views on the Aftermath Influence of Moonlighting on the Performance of LUTH

Fig. 4.10: Responses on Objective Five Variables

APPENDIX
TARABA STATE UNIVERSITY, JALINGO
FACULTY OF MANAGEMENT SCIENCES
DEPARTMENT OF PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION

Questionnaire

This study on moonlighting and employees performance among medical practitioners of Lagos university teaching hospital is being conducted by Adako Dauda in order to under the influence that moonlighting or multiple job holding have on the performance of an individual employee's performance and the overall organization performance. All information received would be used for academic purposes only, and treated in the strictest of confidence.

Thank you.

SECTION A: Demographic Data

Instructions: Please kindly tick {√} against the option that represents your response. Do not write your name on the questionnaire.

1. Gender: Male { } Female { }
2. Age: 20-29 { } 30-39 { } 40-49 { } 50-59 { } 60 & above { }
3. Qualification:
SSCE { }
OND { }
HND { }
Bachelor's Degree { }
Master's Degree { }
Others (please specify)
-
4. How long have you been employed in LUTH?
0-5 years { } 6-10 years { }
11- 15 years { }
16-20 years { }
21 years and above { }

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5. Your Department of operation in LUTH.....
6. Staff Category: Medical doctor { } Nurse { } Pharmacists { } Radiologists { } others, kindly specify.....

SECTION B

Instruction: Please tick [✓] against the appropriate option from each of the following;

Key: SA= Strongly Agree; A= Agree; N= Neutral; D= Disagree; SD= Strongly Disagree

S/N	STATEMENT	SA	A	N	D	SD
	FACTORS THAT NECESSITATES MOONLIGHTING PRACTICE AMONG STAFF OF LUTH					
1.	Staff moonlighting is amongst the problems which medical profession at both national and global level are confronted with. Is staff moonlighting also a problem in LUTH?.					
2.	Staff of LUTH hold other income jobs aside their official job.					
3.	There is extra activity you do in this institution outside your official duty which you are pay for.					
4.	There are extracurricular activities you carry out in LUTH but do not receive monetary compensation?					
5.	Moonlighting diversify staff skill toward quality service.					
	MODE OF STAFF MOONLIGHTING PRACTICE AMONG MEDICAL PRACTITIONERS OF LUTH.					
6.	Staff of LUTH are engage in additional shift practice for more pay.					
7.	Parallel medical services in other health institutions is a common practice among staff of LUTH.					
8.	Most staff of LUTH owns private clinic					
9.	Medical professionals of LUTH consult for private individuals, clinics and NGOs.					
	INFLUENCE OF MOONLIGHTING ON THE PERFORMANCE OF MEDICAL PRACTITIONERS					
10.	Moonlighting affect individual staff performance of LUTH.					

11.	Moonlighting affect staff duty coverage ability.					
12.	Moonlighting affect medical practitioners' dedication to duty.					
	STRATEGIES USE BY MANAGEMENT OF LUTH IN COMBATING MOONLIGHTING AMONG STAFF					
13.	The management of LUTH is happy with staff moonlighting activities.					
14.	LUTH management checkmating moonlighting practice among staff.					
15.	LUTH management penalize staff who moonlight.					
16.	Management establishes a clear direction for addressing staff moonlighting practice.					
17.	You have a colleagues who have been warned or reprimanded by the management due to moonlighting practice?					
	AFTERMATH EFFECT OF MOONLIGHTING ON THE PERFORMANCE OF LUTH.					
18.	Staff moonlighting has negative impact on the overall performance of LUTH.					
19.	Moonlighting affect quality of staff performance.					
20.	Staff moonlighting affect LUTH consistency to quality service delivery.					
21.	LUTH staff are often exhausted because of moonlighting.					